

GENERATION Z PROTESTS IN NEPAL COMPARED WITH THE ARAB SPRING: THE EVOLUTION OF THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract

This article compares the Arab Spring protests in Tunisia and Egypt (2011) with Generation Z protests in Nepal (2025) to examine how the shift from friend-centric networks (Facebook/Twitter) to algorithmically curated ecosystems (TikTok/Discord/Telegram) reshapes mobilisation thresholds, the pace of contention, organisational depth, and political outcomes. Methodologically, it employs a qualitative comparative design based on secondary sources using theoretical criteria: platforms/infrastructure, mobilisation threshold, tempo/volatility, organisational depth (the “signal vs. capacity” ratio), and outcome. The theoretical framework draws on Granovetter and Tufekci, as well as approaches to connective action and affective publics. Findings indicate that digital networks lower participation thresholds and barriers to entry into collective action, thereby accelerating diffusion. In Tunisia and Egypt, social media amplified coordination within existing trade-union and party structures; in Nepal, mobilisation emerged and was coordinated online through horizontal influencer–moderator networks without party backing. Large Discord communities functioned as deliberative hubs and heightened visibility, while viral short-form video produced rapid, affect-driven escalation; yet organisational capacity lagged behind the visible “signal”, and the protest cycle remained short and volatile. Conclusion: the shift to algorithmic feeds increases speed and scale but constrains institutionalisation; durable change still depends on organisational “bridges” that convert visibility into sustained capacity.

Keywords: Generation Z protests; Nepal 2025; Digital mobilisation; Mobilisation threshold; Social media.

1. INTRODUCTION

The 2025 unrest in Nepal, part of a broader wave across Africa and Asia and labelled in public discourse as Generation Z protests, bears multiple resemblances to events in Egypt and Tunisia during the 2011 Arab Spring, which culminated in regime change through mass demonstrations. Common features include youth as the principal protagonists; dissatisfaction with corruption and bleak economic prospects; demographic pressure (a youthful population and high youth unemployment); “leaderless”⁶ movement and

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⁶ The concept of “leaderless movements” refers to decentralised, horizontally organised forms of collective action in which the absence of formal leadership does not imply an absence of coordination; rather, coordination is reconfigured into networked, algorithmically mediated processes of decision-making and influence. Such movements operate through distributed authority, and their cohesion derives from shared moral and symbolic orientations rather than hierarchical structure (Bennett & Segerberg, 2012). Under contemporary socio-digital conditions, “leaderless” models represent a new paradigm of political mobilisation, in which

coordination; and the pivotal role of social media in mobilisation and organisation. The article compares Nepal with Egypt and Tunisia using criteria of volatility (Hale, 2020), mobilisation thresholds (Granovetter, 1978), and the signal-capacity ratio (Tufekci, 2017), alongside relevant theoretical concepts, to provide a synthesis of how protests evolved when digital platforms played a significant role.

2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopts a comparative qualitative approach to examine three cases of mass protest: Tunisia and Egypt during the Arab Spring (2011) and Nepal (2025). The analysis is based on secondary sources: academic literature, reports by international organisations, media analyses, and statistics from relevant institutions (United Nations, World Bank, Transparency International).

This article employs a qualitative comparative case-study design, focusing on three cases (Tunisia, Egypt, and Nepal). The limited number of cases allows for in-depth, context-sensitive analysis of protest dynamics and the role of social media. In terms of case selection, the article follows a most-similar systems logic: Tunisia and Egypt are chosen as paradigmatic cases of the first “wave” of digitally mediated mass uprisings in authoritarian contexts during the Arab Spring, where Facebook and Twitter operated in tandem with trade-union and party infrastructures. Nepal (2025) is selected as a theoretically salient successor case: it exhibits comparable structural conditions, a pronounced youth bulge, high youth unemployment, and entrenched corruption, but takes place in a later communication ecology dominated by TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, and Discord and is largely devoid of organisational backing from parties or unions. Comparing these three cases, which all culminated in leadership change within a short time frame, allows the article to hold constant key socio-demographic and governance pressures while varying the configuration of digital platforms and organisational infrastructures that mediate mobilisation, protest dynamics, and outcomes.

The case studies encompass events in Egypt (2011), Tunisia (2011), and Nepal (2025), with an emphasis on the function and significance of social media in establishing durable foundations for social and political activism. The units of analysis are platforms and the broader digital infrastructure (Facebook/Twitter vs. TikTok/Discord). The criteria by which social media are analyzed across three distinct social and political contexts, hence their roles and modes of influence, are:

- Mobilization threshold (the speed and scale of the response to a trigger)
- Tempo and volatility (the dynamics of event development)
- Organizational depth (the relationship between signaling and capacity)
- Protest outcomes (institutional, political, and social effects)

The theoretical framework integrates both classical and contemporary concepts of mobilization to achieve a multilayered understanding of the key dimensions of digital protest.

collective action emerges from communication networks rather than institutional discipline (Gerbaudo, 2012; Tufekci, 2017).

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Generation Z is most commonly defined as those born between the mid-1990s and the early 2010s, with exact bounds varying by source but often taken as 1995–2010. This generation is frequently described as the first truly “digital generation”, having grown up in a world where the internet was already embedded in everyday life. Unlike previous generations, they have never experienced a reality without digital connectivity (Benítez-Márquez et al., 2022; Katz et al., 2021).

The mobilisation threshold refers to the point at which the number of individuals willing to participate in protest, or the intensity of their grievances, reaches a level sufficient to trigger mass action. Individuals decide to join when they perceive that the risks are outweighed by the benefits, often once they observe that they are “not alone” (Granovetter, 1978; Tufekci, 2017).

Volatility, in this context, refers to the degree of political and social unpredictability. Under high volatility, short-term events – such as spontaneously, digitally coordinated protests – can produce deep systemic consequences for the governing authorities and economic stability (Hale, 2020).

Tufekci draws a key distinction between signals of power and actual capacity. Signal denotes the visible display of strength – mass gatherings, viral content, protest marches – at which digital networks excel by rapidly assembling large crowds and generating striking visual and media effects. Capacity, by contrast, refers to the ability to convert that signal into durable political power: organisational infrastructure, clear demands, bargaining mechanisms, and the ability to sustain pressure over time. Capacity requires structure, leadership, hierarchy, and continuity – features that networked protests often lack because they rely on spontaneity and horizontality (Tufekci, 2017).

Bennett and Segerberg (2012) introduce the concept of “*connective action*” to explain individualised, network-mediated participation grounded in personalised narratives rather than stable organisations. Papacharissi (2015) theorises “*affective publics*”, highlighting the roles of emotion, humour, and anger in the circulation of political messages on platforms. These approaches complement Tufekci’s signal–capacity distinction: affective virality rapidly inflates the signal, while the absence of organisational infrastructure constrains capacity and the longevity of protest cycles.

4. KEY EVENTS

4.1. Tunisia (2011)

Mohamed Bouazizi’s self-immolation in Sidi Bouzid (17 December 2010) escalated within days into a wave of protests across Tunisia. Demonstrators’ demands – combating corruption, unemployment, and repression – were articulated and disseminated via social media. Facebook played a decisive role in transmitting information and connecting activists (Bruns, Highfield, & Burgess, 2013). The protests lasted several weeks and culminated on 14 January 2011, when President Zine el-Abidine Ben Ali, after 23 years in power, fled the country.

4.2. Egypt (2011)

The Egyptian protests began on 25 January 2011, Police Day, as an expression of opposition to corruption, police brutality, and economic stagnation (Howard & Hussain, 2011). Inspired by the success of the Tunisian demonstrations, Egyptian activists used the

internet and social media, most notably the Facebook page “We Are All Khaled Said”, to call citizens to mass mobilization (Eltantawy& Wiens, 2011).

The protests spread from Cairo to Alexandria, Suez, and other cities. The demands became more clearly articulated, evolving from calls for social reforms and justice to explicit demands for President Mubarak’s resignation. Over 18 days of contention, the authorities sought to suppress the movement through a mix of repression and concessions, including the shutdown of internet and mobile networks (Howard & Hussain, 2013). Despite violence and intimidation, on 11 February 2011 President Hosni Mubarak resigned after thirty years in power.

4.3. Nepal (2025)

The immediate catalyst for the protests was a nationwide ban on popular social media platforms, including Instagram and TikTok, which provoked outrage among youth who relied on these platforms for expression, organizing, and economic activity (The New Humanitarian, 2025). Although the ban was later lifted, it only further fueled pre-existing grievances.

A significant mobilizing factor, one that further intensified discontent among youth who felt overlooked and marginalized, was the heavily publicized “nepo kids/nepo babies” controversy (Reuters, 2025). Social media circulated numerous videos showcasing politicians’ children enjoying luxuries unattainable to ordinary citizens, in a country where the average annual income is roughly US\$1,500 (World Bank, 2024).

The protests began on 8 September 2025 and culminated on 9 September, when Prime Minister K. P. Sharma Oli resigned. Over the course of two days, demonstrators mounted mass protests that escalated into unrest, resulting in incursions into state institutions, including parliament and the presidential residence, the latter of which was subsequently set on fire. Having secured the prime minister’s resignation, new elections, and following the deployment of the army to the streets to restore order – with the military assuming a mediating role between the protesters and state institutions, chiefly the president – the protesters succeeded in securing the appointment of their preferred candidate as interim prime minister, bringing the protest to conclusion.

5. SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC AND ECONOMIC CONTEXT

The cases analyzed – Egypt and Tunisia during the Arab Spring (2011) and Nepal (2025) – share structural similarities that made youth mobilization likely and potent: pronounced youth demographic pressure (*youth bulge*⁷), high youth unemployment, and systemic corruption that erodes trust in institutions.

Egypt: According to the United Nations (2011), the 15–29 cohort constituted approximately 27% of the total population. World Bank data for 2010 record youth unemployment at 24.8%, with higher rates among university graduates. The Corruption Perceptions Index (Transparency International, 2010) gave Egypt a score of 3.1/10, indicating widespread public-sector corruption.

⁷ The term *youth bulge* denotes a demographic structure in which the share of young people – most commonly those aged 15-29 – significantly exceeds other age groups within the total population. This phenomenon arises when fertility remains high over an extended period while mortality declines, producing a large cohort entering the labor market and public life simultaneously (Urdal, 2006). In socio-political terms, the youth bulge is frequently associated with an elevated risk of political instability, protest, and violent conflict – especially where high youth unemployment, economic inequalities, and weak institutions are present (Cincotta et al., 2003).

Tunisia: The 15–29 cohort accounted for roughly 25% (United Nations, 2011), and youth unemployment stood at 30.7% (World Bank, 2012). The Corruption Perceptions Index (Transparency International, 2010) assigned a score of 4.3/10, reflecting broad discontent with corruption and the opacity of state institutions.

Nepal: In 2024–2025, the 15–29 cohort represented 27.9% (UNFPA Nepal, 2023); youth unemployment was 20.8%, with high informality (~55%) (World Bank, 2024). The Corruption Perceptions Index (Transparency International, 2024) is 35/100 (rank 108/180), indicating persistently high perceived corruption. Corruption and nepotism remain chronic (Mulmi, 2025). Since 2020, average GDP growth has remained below 5%; remittances account for ~33% of GDP; and about 1,700 people leave the country each day in search of work (Mulmi, 2025).

Table 1. Key sociodemographic and governance indicators

Indicator	Egypt (2010–2011)	Tunis (2010–2011)	Nepal (2024–2025)
Share of population aged 15–29	27% (UN, 2011)	25% (UN, 2011)	27.9% (UNFPA Nepal, 2023)
Youth unemployment (15–24)	24.8% (World Bank, 2010)	30.7% (World Bank, 2010)	20.8% (World Bank, 2024)
Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI)	3.1/10 (Transparency International, 2010)	4.3/10 (Transparency International, 2010)	35/100 (Transparency International, 2024)
CPI rank	98/178	59/178	108/180

6. THE ROLE OF SOCIALMEDIA IN THE SUPPORT STRUCTURE AND ORGANIZATION OF PROTESTS

6.1. Tunisia (2011): Trade-Union Infrastructure as the Backbone of Mobilization

In Tunisia, although the immediate trigger for the mass protests was Mohamed Bouazizi’s self-immolation, the General Union of Tunisian Workers (UGTT) played the key role in transforming spontaneous discontent into an organized movement. Deeply embedded in the country’s social fabric, it was the only institution with the logistical, communicative, and network capacities to mobilize citizens at the national level (Beinin, 2016). The UGTT organized general strikes, coordinated protest sites, and steered the narrative toward political reform, thereby effectively assuming the role of political organizer. Thus, while digital communication was important for disseminating information, the foundation of the Tunisian protests was institutional: mobilization was socially structured rather than purely networked (Alexander, 2011).

The Tunisian case thus illustrates a hybrid pattern: elements of connective action (networked diffusion and personalized narratives) were layered onto existing collective structures (the UGTT and student organizations), while affective impulses were channeled through union infrastructure. In this configuration, a strong social-media signal was translated into mobilizational capacity via institutional bridges.

6.2. Egypt (2011): The Digital Spark Harnessed by Political Actors

Unlike Tunisia, the Egyptian protests began as connective action around the Facebook page We Are All Khaled Said (Howard & Hussain, 2013), but quickly spilled into collective political structures: the April 6 Youth Movement and the Muslim Brotherhood assumed on-the-ground coordination, logistics, and media outreach (Lynch, 2012). Affective publics on social media supplied speed and scale, while organizations provided capacity and continuity. Egypt thus also represents a hybrid model: digitally initiated, politically co-opted. In both Tunisia and Egypt, social media simultaneously accelerated mobilization and heightened international visibility, yet the decisive weight still rested with offline structures (Bruns, Highfield, & Burgess, 2013).

6.3. Nepal (2025): Structureless Digital Self-Organization

The 2025 protests in Nepal exhibit a qualitative shift in the pattern of political mobilization. Unlike the Arab Spring protests, they had no institutional backing. No opposition party participated, and the largest parties – Nepali Congress, CPN-UML, and the Maoist Centre – publicly distanced themselves from the demonstrations (Suwal, 2025). The movement emerged exclusively online, coordinated across TikTok, Discord, and Telegram, where informal moderators and Gen-Z influencers disseminated messages and mobilized crowds. Reports by Amnesty International (2025) and Freedom Forum (2025) describe a “horizontal network of digital nodes,” which enabled viral diffusion while also accelerating the loss of cohesion.

In digital terms, synthesizing telecom and survey data, recent estimates suggest that by January 2025 there were about 16.5 million internet users in Nepal – roughly 55.8% of the population – and some 14.3 million social media user identities, equivalent to 48.1% of the population (DataReportal, 2025; Paudel, 2025). These figures are broadly consistent with World Bank and ITU series, which put internet use at around 55% of the population in 2023 (World Bank, 2024). A recent UNICEF–ChildSafeNet situation paper, drawing on Nepal Telecommunications Authority data, reports that in the first quarter of 2024 there were 42.34 million broadband mobile connections in a country of roughly 29 million inhabitants (about 145% of the population), underscoring the ubiquity of mobile access in everyday life (UNICEF & ChildSafeNet, 2024). Within this environment, Meta’s advertising tools indicate that Facebook⁸ and Instagram alone could reach approximately 14.3 million users – 48.1% of the total population and 72.8% of adults (18+) – while Instagram had around 3.9 million users, or 13.2% of the population, with a clear concentration in the 18–34 age cohort (DataReportal, 2025). In parallel, the Internet Service Providers’ Association of Nepal estimated that TikTok had around 2.2 million users before the November 2023 ban and that TikTok traffic alone accounted for nearly 40% of total internet bandwidth consumption (Prasain, 2023). Taken together, these figures indicate that for connected young Nepalis, social media use is close to universal, with platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and especially TikTok operating less as marginal entertainment apps and more as core

⁸ In order to clarify how the social media environment in Nepal differs from that of Egypt and Tunisia, it is important to note that in the contemporary digital landscape, Facebook and Instagram have largely moved away from their original friend-centred architecture and have progressively adopted TikTok-like recommendation logics. As a result, Facebook now operates much like TikTok or Instagram Reels – as an algorithmic, short-video-dominated discovery feed in which exposure is driven primarily by engagement signals and “interest clusters” rather than by pre-existing social ties (Narayanan, 2023; Gerbaudo, 2024).

infrastructures of everyday communication and identity. This helps explain why attempts to curtail social media access triggered such a strong and sustained Gen Z backlash. In practice, this viral diffusion was carried by highly visual, memetic content, anime-inspired protest flags, ironic placards and short TikTok clips that mixed humour with footage of police violence. These circulated faster than any formal call to protest and made the uprising instantly recognisable as a Gen Z event.

Nepal thus exemplifies a dominant connective action pattern: coordination via TikTok, Discord and Telegram channels, driven by influencers and moderators, without party anchoring. The dynamics were powered by affective publics – emotionally charged, visually forceful, and often ironic video clips –that produced rapid spikes of attention and low thresholds for participation. This mechanism helps explain both the strong initial signal and the brief duration of the cycle, as well as the difficulty of converting that energy into organizational depth. Consequently, the institutionalization of outcomes remains limited despite impressive visibility.

It is important to underscore the unprecedented method through which the candidate for interim prime minister was chosen, and the role of the social platform Discord. During the mass protests, youth movements – primarily students, programmers, and activists from Kathmandu – created the Discord server “Youth Against Corruption,” which quickly grew to more than 100,000 members. Initially, the server was used to coordinate protests, share logistics, document abuses, and raise funds. When a political vacuum emerged (the prime minister resigned and parliament was dissolved), organizers opened dedicated channels for “interim government candidate proposals.” Members anonymously nominated public figures with reputations for integrity, including journalists, judges, and activists. Former Supreme Court Justice Sushila Karki soon emerged as the leading option.

Activists then ran an in-platform poll on Discord; Karki received approximately 3,833 votes out of 7,700 participants, the highest by a wide margin (Mulmi, 2025). This result was relayed to the media and the armed forces. Within 48 hours, the president, under public and international pressure, formalized that choice by appointing Karki as interim prime minister. This episode set a precedent in contemporary political history: for the first time, the selection of the candidate for interim prime minister stemmed from a digital process of deliberation and collective decision-making on a platform originally designed for gaming and social interaction.

7. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The comparative analysis of the selected cases comprises, first, an examination of the platforms employed, with attention to their affordances, and, second, an inquiry guided by the adopted theoretical criteria (Tufekci, 2017): mobilization threshold, pace, organizational depth, degree of violence, and outcomes.

Platforms:

- Egypt & Tunisia (2011): Facebook and Twitter – **sharing premised on friend/follower networks;**
- Nepal (2025): TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, Discord – **operation premised on algorithmic feeds**⁹.

Key implications:

- Speed of diffusion: algorithmic feeds enable content to go viral within hours, whereas friend networks rely on chain sharing.
- Decentralization of authorship: content can originate from anyone; content performance matters more than author identity.
- Affective amplification: algorithms privilege emotionally charged, visually salient, and often polarizing content, spurring collective reactions and a sense of urgency.
- Weaker narrative control: states and legacy media struggle to manage virality because content flows are fragmented and driven by interactions rather than hierarchy.

In the Nepali case, the abstract properties of algorithmic virality were visible in a distinctive visual and memetic repertoire. One strand revolved around pop-cultural symbols, most notably the Straw Hat Pirates' Jolly Roger flag from the anime and manga *One Piece*. Initially circulating within anime fandom and social-media spaces, the flag quickly migrated to the streets: protesters carried it on black banners and, during the fire at Singha Durbar, hung it across the palace gates as a generational emblem of defiance against censorship and corruption (Ratcliffe, 2025). A second strand centered on emotionally charged close-ups, above all the now iconic image of a blood-soaked white sneaker left on the asphalt near the parliament building, which was shared millions of times and came to symbolize the bodily risk and precarity borne by young protesters (Shree et al., 2025.) Short-form TikTok and Instagram videos further combined irony and destruction: clips of teenagers dancing in front of burning government buildings or filming choreographed routines amid tear gas and sirens travelled quickly through recommendation feeds, were endlessly re-uploaded, and picked up by international media (Paul, 2025; NDTV, 2025). These image-meme hybrids circulated faster than any single organizational call, repeatedly resurfacing on "For You" pages, lowering the subjective threshold for participation while simultaneously blurring the line between political witnessing and performative clout-seeking.

⁹ During the first wave of digital activism, the Arab Spring (2011), social media such as Facebook and Twitter operated primarily on friend graphs: network structures formed by direct interpersonal ties (friend–friend or follower–followed). Information diffused horizontally within networks that were fundamentally social rather than algorithmically mediated. In this model, the content a user sees depends on personal ties and direct sharing, which fosters trust and organic diffusion but constrains the speed and scale of reach. By contrast, contemporary platforms such as TikTok, Instagram Reels, Telegram channels, and Discord communities are built around algorithmic feeds – systems in which AI-driven recommendation models determine what content a user sees, independent of personal contacts. These feeds analyze user behavior (watch time, interactions, topical interests) and dynamically push high-engagement content, enabling messages to spread vertically and exponentially, often far beyond the author's primary social graph.

Mobilization threshold: Compared to Egypt and Tunisia, where mass mobilization expanded over time as events unfolded and content was gradually shared (police brutality, regime violence), Nepal saw almost instantaneous mass mobilization; in other words, the mobilization threshold was very low. The visibility of injustice, repression, and corruption through algorithmically propelled short-form video (the so-called *story culture*¹⁰) provides what is perceived as continuous visual evidence for the crowd. This depresses the mobilization threshold and compresses the time from outrage to street-level protest.

Pace and volatility: Egypt and Tunisia – slower onset with prolonged momentum and duration; Nepal – a sharp onset with a short-lived trajectory. The $T_0 \rightarrow T_1$ interval (trigger → first mass mobilization) is shorter than in 2011.

Organizational depth (signal and capacity): In Egypt and Tunisia, social media were employed for promotion and coordination, yet the principal anchors remained offline (trade unions and political parties). In Nepal, organizational structures were shallower: no parliamentary party participated in the protests, and coordination relied on Discord groups with promotion via other social platforms (TikTok, Instagram). The signal was stronger in Nepal, but capacity was weaker. This “signal vs. capacity” distinction underscores that a large, rapidly assembled crowd is not equivalent to organizational strength; as Tufekci shows, this is a structural limitation of networked movements, which is why contemporary outcomes more often take the form of policy concessions rather than deep regime change.

Outcome: Egypt and Tunisia – regime change; Nepal – the fall of the government and the announcement of parliamentary elections within six months, but no sweeping or deep structural transformation.

Table 2. Comparative dynamics of 2011 and 2025 protest waves

	Egypt & Tunisia (2011)	Nepal (2025)	Key implications
Platforms	Facebook, Twitter	TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, Discord	Paradigm shift in communication ecology.
Mobilization threshold	Gradual build-up via time and chain-sharing	Near-instant mobilization; low threshold	Lowered threshold: shortened time from anger to street.
Pace & volatility	Slower onset; longer momentum and duration	Sharp onset; short-lived trajectory; high volatility	Faster cycles increase tactical speed but reduce staying power.
Organizational depth	Social media for promotion/coordination, anchored by robust offline structures (unions, parties)	Coordination via digital groups; no parliamentary parties involved; promotion on TikTok/Instagram	Greater signal , lower capacity : mass turnout ≠ organizational strength.

¹⁰ *Story culture* denotes a digital mode of communication through short-lived, ephemeral narratives (“stories”) that operate as visual and emotional micro-events in real time. In contrast to the static *post culture*, where posts are durable and reflective, *story culture* fosters immediacy, spontaneity, and shared participation. In the context of contemporary social movements, this expressive model enables the rapid diffusion of emotions, moral messages, and micro-narratives that serve as triggers for collective action. (Leaver, Highfield, & Abidin, 2020; Tufekci, 2017).

	Egypt & Tunisia (2011)	Nepal (2025)	Key implications
Outcome	Regime change	Government collapse and parliamentary elections called (without deep systemic transformation)	Contemporary movements more often yield policy concessions than deep political restructurings.

8. CONCLUSION

The case studies support the conclusion that the causes of protest onset are structural in nature –unemployment, corruption, and poverty – accompanied by implicit trigger factors. Of particular importance is that the dynamics of events in 2011 and 2025 differ considerably. An analysis of the structural patterns of social-movement organization in Tunisia (2011) and Egypt (2011), on the one hand, and Nepal (2025), on the other, reveals significant shifts in how political discontent is transformed into collective action. Whereas the Arab Spring protests were anchored in social and political structures – trade unions, opposition parties, and civil-society networks –the 2025 Gen Z protests in Nepal exemplify a mode of near-total digital self-organization, largely without traditional institutional intermediaries. The shift in technological infrastructure from friend-centric networks to algorithmic feeds directly shaped the tempo, scale, and volatility of the protests, enabling faster but also more superficial mobilization.

Put differently, the protests in Tunisia and Egypt belong to an era in which social media served as instruments for organizing pre-existing opposition structures, whereas Nepal exemplifies a period in which social media themselves become a relatively self-sufficient oppositional infrastructure. While, during the Arab Spring, trade unions and opposition parties functioned as bridges between the digital and the street, the Gen Z protests display a fully digitized mode of political mobilization, driven by visibility algorithms, viral formats, and a collective sense of injustice, yet lacking substantive political articulation. One can argue that the protests of 2025 constitute the first wave of “post-organized” contention, in which the network takes on the role of the party and virality substitutes for leadership. Nevertheless, this form of post-organized resistance, though highly visible and affectively intense, often lacks sufficient institutional depth to produce durable political transformations, rendering it effective in the short term but weak over longer horizons.

Looking ahead, the very features that make post-organized contention fragile in institutional terms are also likely to shape future political processes. The Nepali case suggests that generationally concentrated, digitally native cohorts can rapidly alter the tempo and visibility of politics without relying on parties or unions. Over time, this may reinforce a durable generational divide in which Gen Z and younger Millennials experience politics primarily through short-form, algorithmically curated content rather than through programmatic party competition. Electoral campaigns, candidate branding, and issue framing are therefore increasingly likely to follow the logic of personalised, meme-based signalling that Bennett and Segerberg (2012) describe as “connective action,” rather than the organisation-centred repertoires that structured the Arab Spring.

Ultimately, the comparison between the Arab Spring and Nepal’s Gen Z uprising highlights a broader strategic dilemma for digitally mediated contention: how to translate rapid, spectacular visibility into the slow work of building durable organisations and policy

influence. Future research on digital protest will therefore need to focus not only on platforms and protest waves, but also on the intermediate organisational forms – from issue-based collectives to hybrid party–movement structures – that might bridge this gap and avoid what Tufekci (2017) terms “signal-rich, capacity-poor” mobilisation.

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